

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Executive Summary

This deliverable, titled “Sustainable procurement, retail and product tracking and labelling system” aims to find the best fit labelling and tracking systems, analysing the state of the art of the most common and innovative labelling and tracking technologies.

As a first step, before entering into the development of the traceability system, an analysis of the reverse logistics chain associated with the three sectors studied (automotive, furniture and construction) should be carried out, based on the Supply Chain Operations Reference model (SCOR), in order to identify each of the business processes and the agents involved. Specifically, this analysis is developed in *D5.1.-Report on collection and reverse logistics optimization*. For that reason, it is not included in this document.

Hereafter, and based on the study being conducted in *D7.6 - Legal and Regulatory, Environmental, and Health and Safety Requirements*, a SWOT analysis is included in the previous terms, about the development of circular business models related to the three sectors.

This document also covers the Logistics Platform specifications that supports the other software platforms in the WP6. This platform handles the locations and lifecycle tracking of the ECOBULK products and also includes a reverse logistics costs module which constitutes an input to the QAS and DSS Services providing the transportation costs and environmental impact.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Description of the document and pursue

This document first aim is to address the SCOR model related to the reverse logistics of the industry sectors: automotive, furniture and construction (outdoor furniture).

Subsequently, a SWOT analysis is included, related to the definition and implementation of circular business models in these three sectors, taking into considerations issues such as legal, health and safety.

Thereafter, this report addresses the definition and design of a track and trace system, starting with the analysis of the state of the art of the different tracking and labelling technologies available. Furthermore, it explains the development of a Logistics Platform and its specifications.

The intended audience of this document includes the development teams, exploitation stakeholders and operations teams of the ECOBULK project.

This deliverable will be used by the ECOBULK partners as the specification document to know how to connect to the Logistics Platform.

1.2 WPs and Tasks related with the deliverable

This document intends to cover part of the purpose of the task 6.1 which deals with "Sustainable procurement, retail and product tracking and labelling development and implementation".

Furthermore, this task is contained in the work package 6 named "Design and implementation of the Systems, Services and Databases" and this deliverable explains the logistics platform developed and its specification.

Moreover, the content of this document is closely related with work package 5 and more specifically with task 5.1 named "Collection and reverse logistics of the components/products"; additionally, it is also related to the WP8, specifically to the tasks 8.1 "Circular Value Chain

Design” and 8.4 “Business cases of the three types of circular designed products developed”.

2 Reverse logistics model based on the SCOR

This section is developed in the deliverable *D5.1-Report on collection and reverse logistics optimization*, and more specifically in section 3, which describes the SCOR model and applies its methodology to the three industry sectors studied in the project. This analysis includes tables identifying the main activities carried out, the agents involved and the most important costs.

3 SWOT analysis related to the new circular models

This study is based on the analysis develop in WP7 “Life Cycle Thinking for the circular designed products”, tasks taking into account the existing regulations for the processes of recovery of materials in the automotive, construction and furniture sectors, as well as other factors such as safety and health criteria (from the point of view of the consumer and the worker of the companies that are going to carry out these processes of recovery of the materials).

Specifically, a life cycle approach enables product designers, service providers, government agents and individuals to make choices for the longer term and with consideration of all environmental media (i.e., air, water, land). Life cycle approaches avoid shifting problems from one life cycle stage to another, from one geographic area to another and from one environmental medium (for example air quality) to another (for example water or land).

In this context, the main benefits form this approach are:

- **Benefits for Industries:** benefits of environmental, occupational health and safety, risk and quality management can be identified as well as developing and applying cleaner process and product options.

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- **Benefits for Governments:** Governmental initiatives will not only secure and strengthen the position of the industrial and service sectors in regional and global markets, but also ensure overall environmental benefits to society (balanced with economic and social aspects).
 - **Benefits for Consumers:** life cycle approaches will help point consumption in a more sustainable direction by offering better information for purchasing, transport systems, energy sources, to guide consumers.

One critical point is the consumer's perception. In fact, consumer decisions have an enormous impact on the transition to a circular economy, and consumers need to be empowered with consumer rights and access to reliable information to be able to play their role in the circular economy to the full extent about this project. In general, prices of products do not always reflect their environmental and societal costs, which reduces the incentives to produce and consume sustainably. As a result, most products are discarded at the end of their service life and their materials are not sufficiently recycled, causing valuable resources to be wasted, including critical raw materials

As is abundantly clear, economic aspects are crucial. In order to strengthen and encourage circular business models, some initiatives can be address. In this scenario, economic incentives for reusing recycled materials can be adopted. There is some experience with applying EPR or reduced VAT rates. Shifting from taxation on labour to other tax bases less detrimental to economic growth, such as consumption taxes and environmental taxes, would contribute to pricing in negative externalities, incentivise behavioural change and support the transition to a Circular Economy.

a) Transport and mobility:

Several policies are in place at different levels to increase the sustainability of this sector along the whole value chain. At the EU level, a comprehensive policy framework is in place, addressing vehicle emissions and setting requirements for safety, security and passenger rights. Covering all developments in this field is beyond the reach of this analysis, which focusses on products. Developments in electric mobility will clearly impact the use of Lithium Ion batteries, already touched on the particular importance of repair, reuse and remanufacturing in the automotive sector, given the high value of the products being used. When vehicles reach end-of-life, they are covered by the end-of-life vehicles (ELV directive, which includes mandatory EPR).

Much potential for circular economy remains in this sector, including uptake of more environmentally friendly cars and improved consumer information as well as addressing waste from ships.

b) Furniture:

More than a quarter of the world's furniture is produced in the EU, representing a market of around 84 billion euros. Furniture producers in the EU are mainly SMEs. The EU is a net exporter of furniture, but production outside the EU is increasing faster than within and with it the amount of imported furniture. Furniture produced in the EU often consists of certified wood and generally enjoys long product lifetimes, but there are indications that these long lifetimes are decreasing and reuse options with them¹. In some cases, shorter product lifetime may be caused by an increase in the use of plastic, chipboard and medium

¹ See <http://eeb.org/cutting-waste-could-boost-furniture-industry/>

density fibreboard (MDF) to replace more durable but more expensive solid wood and metal. Where reuse does occur, it is mostly through commercial second-hand shops, social enterprise companies/ charities and furniture lease companies. Some items are also exchanged via free and paid online platforms, though the number of items traded in this way is difficult to estimate.

Furniture can maintain its value over time, indeed even becoming more valuable as antiques in some cases. Low-cost furniture can fulfil short-term needs affordably but is more likely to be discarded in the event of moving to a new house or office and less likely to be repaired in case of damage. Approximately 10 million tons of furniture are discarded in the EU every year. Recycling of the materials takes place, for instance in the wood-based panel industry², however overall recycling rates for furniture are estimated at only 10%³.

The long product lifetimes of (high-quality) furniture mean that issues with legacy chemicals are particularly relevant in this sector. For example, some flame-retardants that have been phased out still occur in furniture, calling reuse and recycling in question.

Furniture appears to be a sector where second-hand purchases are a popular option, with 55% indicating they regularly buy furniture in the second-hand market (with 25% preferring new furniture and the rest expressing no opinion). From the stakeholder workshops, the public consultation and policy papers from the sector itself⁴, it is clear that stakeholders are interested in developing EU policy tools in pursuit of more circular design of furniture, taking into account the whole life cycle. EPR was

² <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9b823034-ebad-11e8-b69001aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-80148793>

³ Forthcoming study, to be published on <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/enveco/studies.htm>

⁴ e.g. www.efic.eu/public/documents/EFIC%20policy%20paper%20Circular%20Economy.pdf

considered a good instrument in this context, but the stakeholders called for harmonised application across the EU, including the rules on fee modulation. Reparability could be improved by better disassembly options. Further encouragement of circular public procurement is also called for.

In conclusion, there appears to be large remaining potential in the furniture sector, specifically with material substitution, increased recycling and/or increased reuse or preparing for reuse. Enhanced uptake of EU Ecolabel and GPP criteria could realise some of this potential. Requirements on circular design of furniture and/or EPR measures could further achieve results.

c) Buildings and Construction Products:

The construction sector has large potential for circular economy given the scale of material use, value contained in buildings, labour intensiveness and long-term effect of measures. Overall, the construction sector provides 18 million direct jobs and contributes to about 9% of the EU's GDP. It is one of the most resource consuming sectors in Europe - it accounts for approximately half of all extracted materials, half of total energy consumption and one third of water consumption. Construction and demolition waste (CDW) accounts for approximately 25% - 30% of all waste generated in the EU with very significant life cycle impacts, particularly associated with extraction and processing stages. The level of recycling and material recovery of CDW varies greatly (between less than 10% and over 90%) between EU Member States.

the improvement of energy performance of buildings within the EU. These instruments focus on energy performance in the operational phase and as such, do not cover overall life cycle performance within the meaning of circular economy.

As a first step, and as an action in the Circular Economy Action Plan, the European Commission, in collaboration with a large number of building professionals, has developed a tool to assess and report on sustainability aspects throughout the lifetime of buildings⁵. The tool is called Level(s)⁶. The objective is to provide a common language on sustainability and circularity for buildings, with a tool that is targeting the mainstream market. It should be an easy entry point to sustainability assessment, also for all those building projects which currently consider such assessment as being too complex. Level(s) will increase knowledge across the market and will gradually allow standard building projects to improve building performance in a cost-efficient way and enable comparability, exchange of good practice and benchmarking. This common language and the knowledge that it generates can in turn be used in different initiatives to incentivize circular buildings, such as Green Public Procurement, building passport concept and market initiatives. Currently direct reuse of construction products such as doors, windows or frames does not take place at large scale. Increased reuse, in particular of beams and frames of steel or wood, could have a significant positive impact in terms of CO₂ emission equivalents. The accompanying reduction in production and sales would have a (smaller) negative impact on employment and economic value. Better recycling of doors, flat glass and window frames containing PVC holds further promise⁷.

In conclusion, further potential for circularity remains in this sector. Assessments of sustainability performance over the life

⁵ The tool is coherent with existing EU legislation in the field, e.g. the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive, and includes existing energy performance standards and metrics within its broader sustainability scope.

⁶ <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/eussd/buildings.htm>

⁷ Forthcoming study, to be published on <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/enveco/studies.html>

cycle could be made more mainstream by enhancing their accessibility and by public authorities gradually starting to request such information. This could lead to better understanding and consistent measurement of the whole life carbon emissions and other sustainability aspects of built projects, in turn allowing for comparability of results, benchmarking and target setting to e.g. optimise overall carbon reductions. Also, long-term thinking past project completion could be promoted concerning maintenance, durability and lifespan, deconstruction, recycling and adaptability of building components or projects as a whole. This could also lead to better reuse of construction products such as windows, doors and frames. Market incentives promoting sustainability are important in this sector, as payback times for investments in circularity typically are linked to the building performance over the full lifetime, which is long for buildings.

In summary, the following frameworks show the main figures identified as a result of a SWOT analysis related to the definition and implementation of circular business models in the three sectors.

STRENGTHS

- EU legislation and Action Plan for Circular Economy
- Some sustainable and recycling systems implemented
- Environmental and health protection
- No cost of sustainable management for local authorities
- Job creation opportunities
- Recovery of raw material and contributes to the reduction of emissions or environmental pollution from waste (used products)
- Price/affordability: competitive products against new ones (not circular economy)

WEAKNESSES

- Requires basic organization for developing an optimized value chain
- Lack of regulation and standards for specific procedures (quality)
- Lack of information to the consumer
- Participation of local authorities in the citizens "information campaign"
- Expensive methodology to treat and re-manufacture some products
- Need of incentives for private companies to boost these models

OPPORTUNITIES

- Possibility of land recovery from old quarries and waste dumps or to be used for other activities.
- Funding opportunities
- Positive political profile with increased acceptance levels from citizens
- Population awareness of sustainability and recycling needs

THREATS

- Possible difficulties in cooperation between local authorities and management systems, particularly in island
- If can be ensure standards of quality rates, there may be a loss of confidence by users

4 Labelling system

This paragraph aims to define the labelling system to be developed in the project. To this end, the first step is to make a state-of-the-art study related to the available technologies. Afterwards, the analysis of all the technologies identified will allow to select the most appropriate option.

4.1 Identification of existing technologies

BARCODE

A barcode is an optical machine-readable representation of data relating to the object or product to which is linked or attached. Barcode systems help businesses and organizations to track products, prices, and stock levels for centralized management in a computer software system allowing for incredible increases in productivity and efficiency. Traditional barcoding is paired with the Universal Product Code (UPC) and accounts for billions of scans all over the world every day. Initially barcodes represented data by changing the widths and spacings of parallel lines (known as linear or one-dimensional (1D) barcodes). Later 2D codes were developed using all sort of geometric patterns in two dimensions, which allows barcodes to hold more data than the traditional method. Product data is encoded in both horizontal and vertical dimensions and, as more data is encoded, the size of the barcode can be increased in both the horizontal and vertical directions thus maintaining a manageable shape for easy scanning and product packaging specifications ("2D Barcodes Explained", 2007; Shaked, Levy, Baharavl, & Yen, 2001).

Conventional 1D barcode (Code 39)

2D Barcode (PDF417)

Source: White, Gardiner, Prabhakar, and Razak/A Comparison of Barcoding and RFID Technologies in Practice (2007)

Barcodes originally needed of special optical scanners called barcode readers to be read. However, currently it is possible to read any barcode with a simple smartphone through an app.

The use of barcodes became commercially successful and almost universal thanks to supermarket checkout systems and its need of automation. Nowadays, the use of barcodes has spread to many other tasks that are generically referred to as automatic identification and data capture (AIDC) and it's the most extended system in the AIDC market thanks to its simplicity and low cost.

QR

QR code (abbreviated from Quick Response Code) is a machine-readable two-dimensional barcode defined by the industrial standard ISO/IEC18004:2006 (Standardization, 2006), developed and protected by the Japanese company Denso Wave Incorporated in 1994, which is a member of Toyota group. A QR code uses four standardized encoding modes (numeric, alphanumeric, byte/binary, and kanji) to store data efficiently; extensions may also be used.

Each QR consists on an array of black (logical "1") and white (logical "0") squares, typically used for storing URLs or other information. The modules are evenly distributed in a square net of fields, where the size of a field is the size of a single module. By the standard ISO/IEC18004 one module should be sized 4 x 4 px (pixels) with the print resolution of 300 dpi (dots per inch). This size ensures readability by the majority of optical devices. Each QR code symbol consists of Function Patterns and Encoding Regions. Function patterns do not contain the encoded data (L. Tarjan et al. / Computers and Electronics in Agriculture 109 (2014))

All QR codes have a square shape and include three square outlines in the bottom-left, top-left, and top-right corners which define the orientation of the code. The dots within the QR code contain version and format information together with the content itself. QR codes also include a certain level of error correction, defined as L, M, Q, or H. A low amount of error correction (L) allows the QR code to store more content, while higher error correction (H) makes the code easier to scan in case the code is deteriorated.

Source: L. Tarjan et al. / A readability analysis for QR code application in a traceability system (2014)

The use of QR codes became extensive out of the automotive industry due to its quick readability and greater storage capacity compared to standard UPC barcodes. QR codes can be used for, e.g., **product tracking**, item identification, time tracking, document management, general marketing...

In addition, QR code can be printed directly by applying toner powder of the laser printer to the packaging material, or by using specialized lasers (for example, Marking Lasers) for engraving the QR codes in the packaging material.

The creator of every code can track several information about the following issues:

- number of times a code was scanned
- associated action taken after the scan
- operating system of the devices that scanned the code.

However, dynamic QR codes offer more functionality. The owner can edit the code at any time and can aim a specific individual for personalized marketing. Such codes can track more specific information, including the scanner name and email address, how many times they scanned the code and, in conjunction with tracking codes on a website, conversion rates.

RFID

RFID (acronym for Radio Frequency IDentification) is a type of wireless communication that uses electromagnetic or electrostatic coupling in the radio frequency portion of the electromagnetic spectrum to uniquely identify an object, animal or person. This system constitutes a data collection technology that uses electronic tags for storing data. These tags, also known as an "electronic labels," "transponders" or "code plates," are made up of an RFID chip attached to an antenna. Tags may be battery-powered or get their power from the radio frequency waves coming from the reader. They can transmit in the kilohertz, megahertz and gigahertz ranges.

Like barcodes, RFID tags constitute a way of identifying items. However, barcodes need to be in proximity and line of sight to the scanner for reading, while RFID tags do not require line of sight and can be embedded within packages. Besides, depending on the type of tag and reading application, they can be read at a varying range of distances.

RFID is considered as a revolutionary information exchange system that can create an environment in which every object can be automatically recognised, tracked, and traced from factory to shelf only using a single tag on each product item or pallet (Jones, Clarke-Hill, Shears, Comfort, & Hillier, 2004; Jones, Clarke-Hill, Hillier, & Comfort, 2005; Lai et al, 2005; Ranky, 2006; Sellitto, Burgess, & Hawking, 2007).

Source: www.prometec.net/los-rfid

A RFID system is typically formed by a transceiver, its associated antenna and the transponders (tags) that carry the data. With passive tags the reader transmits a low-power radio signal through the antenna that the tag receives via its own antenna to power an integrated chip.

Using the energy it gets from the signal, the tag briefly converses with the reader for verification and the exchange of data. Once the reader receives the data, it can be sent to a controlling computer and stored in a database for further processing and analysis. Active tags perform in the same way as passive; the difference is that active tags transmit a signal through its antenna continually using power from an internal battery. This appears to be a segment of the RFID market that is growing particularly quickly ("Active RFID Market Surging," 2007).

The following table shows a quick comparison between passive and active RFID tags:

	Passive	Active
<i>Signal strength</i>	Weaker	Stronger
<i>Signal availability</i>	Responds when read	Always on
<i>Size</i>	Smaller	Larger
<i>Initial cost</i>	Lower	Higher
<i>Maintenance</i>	Indefinite lifetime	Replace every 2-3 years
<i>Environment</i>	Available for all environments	Available for all environments

Table 1 - Source: RFID Implementation, Testing & Deployment

While passive and active tags operate in very different ways, they still carry the same information, known as the Electronic Product Code (EPC). This is a product numbering system that uses an additional set of numbers compared to barcodes and assigns each item manufactured with a unique product identification number. The EPC system is linked to an online database that increases the opportunity for information sharing. As the information is stored in only one place it makes changing information, such as item destinations and number of products, much easier. This also means that a product's path through a supply chain can be closely monitored and reviewed (Atkinson, 2005; Furness, 2005; Prater et al., 2005).

RFID technology has many advantages for implementation in automated identification and traceability systems, such as the amount of data that can be contained in a tag, high reading speed of data, possibility of simultaneous reading of multiple tags, and possibility of non-contact reading of data. One of the major disadvantages of RFID technology is the price of its implementation and single tags. This disadvantage affects the use of RFID technology in food product traceability systems, as the price of an RFID tag would greatly affect the price of a single food product. On the other hand, two-dimensional codes can store less but still a significant amount of data and are not costly like RFID tags. They have other disadvantages, including the

need for proximity of readers while reading labels, as well as the influence of the packaging condition to the code readability (L. Tarjan et al. / A readability analysis for QR code application in a traceability system (2014))

One of the biggest benefits RFID provides is that items can be traced across the supply chain and can be located in a warehouse within seconds. This is a very attractive advantage to businesses as they seek to make their supply chains more efficient and reduce waste, theft, and errors (Karkkainen, 2003; Prater, Frazier, & Reyes, 2005; Ranky, 2006; "RFID still brings more questions", 2007; Sheffi, 2004; Wyld 2006). While adoption rates within supply chains have increased rapidly in the past few years (Furness, 2005; Ranky, 2006; Wyld 2006), there are still many retailers that have held back from RFID implementation as they believe that the technology is still not entirely proven and will wait to see the benefits other retailers can generate (Lai, Hutchinson, & Zhang, 2005; Prater et al., 2005; Stevenson, 2004; Vijayaraman & Osyk, 2006).

Much of the literature promotes the benefit and cost savings that companies can gain by implementing RFID, from reductions in waste to more accurate stock information and faster scanning of inbound product (Atkinson, 2005; Clarke, Gosain, & Thillairajah, 2005; "RFID still brings more questions," 2007; Vijayaraman & Osyk 2006;). There are, however, additional costs and issues associated with implementing a project such as RFID that companies must consider. These include internationally agreed-upon operating standards, consumer privacy concerns, further system technological integration, data storage issues, software/hardware maintenance and upgrade costs, and employee training (Clarke et al., 2005; "E-Pedigrees," 2007; Fontelera, 2007; Furness, 2005; Lai, et al, 2005; Porter, 2006; Strauch, 2007; Vijayaraman & Osyk 2006). According to Brewer (2007) a hybrid RFID-barcode system is a viable compromise.

4.2 Assessment and evaluation.

Based on the previous dissertation we can compare the different labelling systems in the following table to assess which one will be the most suitable for the purpose of this project:

COMPARISON	Barcode	QR Code	RFID tag
<i>Line of sight required for reading</i>	YES	YES	NO
<i>Multiple codes/tags can be read simultaneously</i>	NO	NO	YES
<i>Identification capability</i>	Just the type of item	Can identify a specific item	Can identify a specific item
<i>Manual / Automatic tracking</i>	Manual	Manual	Automatic
<i>Updatable information</i>	NO	YES (just the dynamic codes)	YES
<i>Can be read if damaged or dirty</i>	NO	YES (depending on the error correction)	YES

Table 2 – Comparison among the different labelling systems

4.3 Labelling system choice

Based on the previous assessments, the QR code technology is a very good choice. One of the most significant advantages of QR code use for circular economy and reverse logistics comes from its simple technological base: QR code-based technology provides high ease of access for users, because it requires no special tags (such as RFID tags).

QR codes creation is very easy and simple since they can be printed on any surface (e.g., paper or plastic labels or any other surface) and they do not require any sophisticated equipment, just a printer is enough (García-Betances and Huerta 2012; Soon 2008; Denso 2011). Since smartphones are widely spread and used across many life domains, reading and decoding QR codes has become much easier than using systems based on a more complex technology.

A QR code system has another advantage over RFID-based systems: because reading QR codes requires closer proximity, it is almost impossible to read an undesired code. From this perspective, QR code

reading is unambiguous, as it only requires close proximity of the reader device to the item to read the code (García-Betances and Huerta 2012; Soon 2008; Denso 2011).

QR code-based technology is also superior in other ways, such as higher data storage capacity, lower implementation cost, technical simplicity, widespread use, and widely available, free programs for reading and decoding by camera-equipped smartphones. These features make this technology attractive for identification purposes (García-Betances and Huerta 2012. Evaluation and implementation of QR Code Identity Tag system for Healthcare in Turkey - Vassilya Uzun and Sami Bilgin 2016)

Given the advantages of the QR codes, this will be the labelling system used on our use case.

5 Tracking system

Tracking and tracing is a process carried out in logistics or distribution of goods, where the goods which are being transported are monitored as per their locations, characteristics, processes, dates and times...

Tracking in logistics is critically important for it to be successful. Reverse logistics and circular economy imply a changing environment, and it is often necessary to adjust the flow of materials to prevent shortages, over-supply or lost items. Logistics tracking provides the real-time information of the supply chain allowing adjustments to be made if needed.

Likewise, with the aim of developing a tracking system more adapted to the stakeholders' requirements and needs, the process includes:

- Identification and analysis of best practices
- Definition of KPIs to be considered
- Identification of risks and barriers and measures proposition to adopt in order to mitigate them.

5.1 Tracking Best Practices

Traceability in the reverse logistics requires that the processes of internal and external traceability will be effectively carried out. Each stakeholder should be able to identify the direct source and direct recipient of traceable items as they belong to their process.

The implication is not that every logistics chain stakeholder knows absolutely all the data related to a particular item's traceability, but rather proof that relevant members/partners in the logistics chain have done their jobs properly and that information can be accessed if needed.

Consequently, the application of the one-step-forward-one-step-back principle is needed and, further, distribution channel participants need to collect, record, store, and share minimum pieces of information for traceability. To have an effective traceability system across the logistics chain:

- Any item that needs to be traced forward or backward should be identified with a globally unique identifier.
- A common good practice when dealing with tracking in the reverse logistics is that it is not only about materials, but also

about working together and sharing knowledge. It is needed to know who the partners are and connect in partnership. The aim should be connecting the two components: materials/products and the managing tools to control the circular production. If it is not clear who the producers are, how the chain works and where, it is impossible to share knowledge, manage the chain, make new innovations and act responsible together.

(<http://dutchawareness.com/chainmanagement>) All chain participants should implement both internal and external traceability practices.

- Implementation of internal traceability should ensure that the necessary linkages between material inputs and outputs are maintained.
- Use an automatic batch tracking system in order to enter information about all the products within your batch. A "batch" refers to a particular set of goods that were produced together and which used the same materials. Batch tracking is sometimes referred to as lot tracking, and it's a process for efficiently tracing goods along the distribution chain using batch numbers. (<https://dearsystems.com/inventory-management-best-practices/>)

Important considerations for an effective traceability system include:

- Trading partners
- Product and processing
- The products that a company uses or creates
- The logistic units that a company receives or ships
- Inbound and outbound shipments
- Date and time metrics as appropriate

Stakeholders are encouraged to adopt electronic messaging protocols to facilitate the exchange of essential business information using unit identification as a connector between goods and information flow. Companies are also encouraged to adopt standardized interfaces (protocols for two-way communication) for sharing essential traceability event information within a network, thereby allowing

reduction of the substantial size of data transmission along the supply chain (<https://lowrysolutions.com/blog/the-best-practices-in-food-traceability>).

5.2 System KPIs definition

In order to assess if the tracking system is working properly, we can identify several KPIs that can be measured. They are the following:

- **Readability:** Number of successful readings, success reading rate, number of failed readings...
- **Reliability:** Number of lost items
- **Missing information:** Number of codes with blank, wrong or incomplete information
- **Strength:** Number of damaged codes
- **Connectivity:** Number of connection errors
- **Information accessibility:** Easiness in getting and modifying the information

5.3 Risks and barriers

The risk factors that affect traceability can be divided into two main categories, technical risk factors and managerial risk factors (Fotopoulos et al, 2009; Luning et al, 2007). The technical risk factors are the factors which occur during the development, application and innovation concerning traceability technology. Such as the information identification technology, the information collection technology, the information exchange technology, the logistics tracking technology. The application of any new technology requires a testing period. During this period, the authenticity of the traceability activities is easily influenced, distorted or un-collectable. This will decrease the quality of the results of traceability and increase the risk.

The managerial risk factors are focused on the existing and potential human-centered risk factors. During the process of traceability, they

are locating in the various parts of the logistics chain. For instance, data loss or fraud, warehouse pollution, transport problems, traceability standards differences, etc. In comparison with the technical risk factors, managerial risk factors are much more complex and more difficult to control. ("Research on the risk factors affecting food traceability in the food supply chain", He Ma, 2013)

Traceability processes are only as good as the weakest link. Therefore, it is important for everyone in the supply chain to understand the value of collecting and maintaining product information that supports, at the very least, one-step-forward-one-step-back traceability.

The best way to maintain traceability for suppliers, retailers, processors, wholesalers, distributors... is to capture agreed upon traceability information, at critical traceability events, and make the data available via a virtual traceability network using either a 3rd-party solution provider or a company's own databases with standardized web service interfaces and messages (<https://lowrysolutions.com/blog/the-best-practices-in-food-traceability>)

6 Methodology for the environmental impact assessment

The waste collection and transport imply negative externalities such as deterioration of the environment, traffic congestion, accidents... Road transport is responsible for 20% of greenhouse gas emissions, which generates many environmental problems in cities, progressively worsening the quality of life of its citizens.

Approximately 20% of the trips in the city belong to commercial vehicles, generating 25% of CO₂ emissions and the consumption of 50% of fuel dedicated to transportation. Due to its importance, a series of key environmental indicators (KPIs) have been selected to study the environmental impact. These KPIs include both, the environmental impact associated with the vehicle itself (local pollution) and the impact caused by the production of the energy (fuel), which is known as "Wheel source assessment". This study is developed only considering the transportation phase on the whole ECOBULK project.

6.1 6.1. Environmental indicators

The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2003) defines an indicator as "a parameter, or the value resulting from a set of parameters, that offers information about a phenomenon, and that has a broader meaning than that strictly associated to it". The OECD was the pioneer in the use of environmental indicators, and these were developed to respond to society's concern for those environmental aspects of economic and social development. For the definition of environmental indicators carried out in this chapter, the "Climasig" portal of the Ministry of Environment and Territorial Planning of the Junta de Andalucía has been considered. In accordance with the information provided by Climasig, the indicators quantify the information through the aggregation of multiple and different data. In this way, an environmental indicator is a variable that, through the synthesis of environmental information, aims to reflect the state of the environment, or of some aspect of it, at a given time and space. For this reason, it acquires great value as a tool in the processes of evaluation and political decision-making on environmental problems.

An environmental indicator must therefore meet a series of fundamental requirements:

- Measurable and comparable.

-
- Predictive, so you can alert about a negative evolution.
 - Based on reliable and good quality data.
 - Representative of the whole.
 - Sensitive to changes that occur in the middle or in human activities related to it.
 - Scientifically valid, being based on a good knowledge of the described system.
 - Simple, provide a simple and clear information for any user.
 - Good cost-effectiveness balance.

The indicators depend on the notion of the environment that is adopted; This is often associated with the notion of a problem and, therefore, the indicators tend to assess the situation of the main environmental problems. Although indicators are also developed to evaluate the results of environmental policies and those related to the integration of environmental aspects in economic and sectoral policies.

For environmental evaluation, some indicators can be the following:

- **Distance travelled:** is the total length of the path made by a moving object between two points. In our case, it will be the existing distance from a starting point (A) to a point of arrival (B) of the planned route and the units will be kilometres (km). Although, for the election of the route the fastest route will be taken into account and not the shortest route. To obtain the distance travelled will be made using tools such Google Maps or a similar open source provider.
- **Time travelled:** determined period during which an action is carried out or an event takes place. In the project, it is the time since the vehicle leaves the waste manager depot, until it returns to the facilities once the route is completed. The units are minutes (min) or hours (h). The time factor will be more important than others in the choice of routes, since priority will be given to the fastest route versus the shortest distance.
- **Collections performed:** number of collections performed during the course of the route. The unit will be the total number of collections.
- **Fuel consumption:** amount of fuel consumed by the vehicle to carry out the programmed route. The units are litres of diesel (l). The calculation of consumption is usually used for every 100 km of distance

travelled (l/100km). These are data that we can obtain from the technical specifications of the vehicles.

- **Energy consumed:** amount of energy associated with the amount of fuel consumed by the vehicle to carry out the planned route. The units are mega-joules (MJ).

- **Carbon footprint:** amount of greenhouse gases (GHG) emitted into the atmosphere when the programmed route is carried out. The units are kilograms of CO₂ equivalent (kg CO₂ eq.). This indicator is used in many studies, either to calculate the carbon footprint of organizations (GHGs issued in a period of time by an organization) or products and/or services (GHGs issued throughout the life cycle of the product and/or service analysed).

If we obtain the Kg CO₂ eq. per kilometre travelled, we will simply have to multiply those kilograms by the total number of kilometres of the route.

Two methodologies can be followed in order to calculate the carbon footprint for each of the routes:

- Evaluation from deposit to wheels: it would be the emission of CO₂ equivalent of the vehicle only, without considering the quantity emitted by the production of fuel.
- Evaluation from source to wheels: it is the set of equivalent CO₂ emissions, taking into account vehicle emissions and fuel production.

- **NO_x emissions:** taking into account the provisions of the State Register of Emissions and Pollutant Sources (PRTR), nitrogen oxides are a group of gases composed of nitric oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂). The term NO_x refers to the combination of both substances. This type of gases come mainly from the fuels used in the engines of vehicles or industrial processes.

As indicated by the PRTR, inhalation in high concentrations and for a short period of time, can cause pulmonary oedema whose effects are not noticeable until a few hours after the inhalation, aggravated by physical effort. A prolonged exposure can affect the immune system and the lung, resulting in a lower resistance to infections and cause irreversible changes in the lung tissue. With respect to the impacts produced in the environment, it is a substance that has a great importance in the formation of photochemical smog.

- **Emissions of CO:** Based on the information provided by the State Register of Emissions and Pollutant Sources (PRTR), carbon monoxide is an odourless, colourless, tasteless, toxic and highly flammable gas, although it is not irritating. What your exposure can go completely unnoticed. It is less heavy than air, so it accumulates in high areas of the atmosphere.

The main source of carbon monoxide emission occurs in the transport sector due to the incomplete combustion of gas, oil, gasoline, coal and oils. Its inhalation, in small concentrations, can lead to mental confusion, vertigo, headache, nausea, weakness and loss of consciousness. If prolonged or continuous exposure occurs, the nervous system and the cardiovascular system may be affected, leading to neurological and cardiac alterations.

- **PM10 particulate emissions:** to conclude with the types of emissions, PRTR defines PM10 as those solid or liquid particles of dust, ash, soot, metal particles, cement or pollen, dispersed in the atmosphere, and whose diameter varies between 2.5 and 10 µm.

77.9% of the total amount of PM10 emitted comes from the re-suspended dust in the atmosphere. The industry, construction and commerce with 7.6% and the transport rolled with 6.5% represent other focal points of contamination of special relevance. Prolonged or repeated exposure to PM10 can cause harmful effects on the respiratory system of the person.

Finally, after a brief explanation of the methodology employed, we will expose the most interesting results obtained using the SimaPro tool, which is a life cycle assessment (LCA) software package. These results are the several substances and particles emitted by the different vehicle types.

Table 3 – Climate change

	Kg CO2 eq t/km
Lorry > 32 mt EURO5	0,0641
Lorry 16-32 mt EURO5	0,139
Lorry 7,5-16 mt EURO5	0,178
Lorry 3,5-7,5 mt EURO5	0,411
Light commercial vehicle	1,477

Table 4 – Ozone depletion

	kg PM2.5 eq t/km
Lorry > 32 mt EURO5	2,7745E-05
Lorry 16-32 mt EURO5	7,1328E-05

Lorry 7,5-16 mt EURO5	4,57413E-05
Lorry 3,5-7,5 mt EURO5	0,000117534
Light commercial vehicle	0,000825344

Table 5 – Particulate matter

	kg CFC-11 eq t/km
Lorry > 32 mt EURO5	1,1683E-08
Lorry 16-32 mt EURO5	2,57779E-08
Lorry 7,5-16 mt EURO5	3,25412E-08
Lorry 3,5-7,5 mt EURO5	7,51929E-08
Light commercial vehicle	2,72909E-07

Table 6 – Photochemical ozone formation

	kg NMVOC eq t/km
Lorry > 32 mt EURO5	0,000195422
Lorry 16-32 mt EURO5	0,000457922
Lorry 7,5-16 mt EURO5	0,000557573
Lorry 3,5-7,5 mt EURO5	0,00119688
Light commercial vehicle	0,00855564

Table 7 – Freshwater eutrophication

	kg P eq t/km
Lorry > 32 mt EURO5	8,68771E-08
Lorry 16-32 mt EURO5	1,91696E-07
Lorry 7,5-16 mt EURO5	2,41964E-07
Lorry 3,5-7,5 mt EURO5	5,59113E-07
Light commercial vehicle	2,23306E-06

Table 8 – Marine eutrophication

	kg N eq t/km
Lorry > 32 mt EURO5	6,47476E-05
Lorry 16-32 mt EURO5	0,000153173
Lorry 7,5-16 mt EURO5	0,000185467
Lorry 3,5-7,5 mt EURO5	0,000393362
Light commercial vehicle	0,002593583

Table 9 – Land use

	kg C deficit t/km
Lorry > 32 mt EURO5	0,000527211
Lorry 16-32 mt EURO5	0,001163296
Lorry 7,5-16 mt EURO5	0,001468366
Lorry 3,5-7,5 mt EURO5	0,003392989
Light commercial vehicle	0,013092041

Table 10 – Water resource depletion

	m³ water eq t/km
Lorry > 32 mt EURO5	1,17824E-05
Lorry 16-32 mt EURO5	2,59966E-05
Lorry 7,5-16 mt EURO5	3,28204E-05
Lorry 3,5-7,5 mt EURO5	7,58369E-05
Light commercial vehicle	0,000279511

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

GA NUMBER: 730456

Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 31/05/2021

ECOBULK

7 Logistics Platform functionalities

The objective of this section is to explain the methodology followed by the reverse logistics module, the database and the API implementation of the Logistics Platform.

7.1 Reverse Logistics Module

The methodology described in this chapter has been used to calculate the transportation costs per km of different vehicle types. It is based on the ACOTRAM platform developed by the Spanish Ministerio de Fomento (Ministry of Transport and Public Works).

Hereafter, an annual cost calculation will be briefly described. These costs don't include the VAT since it is considered neutral in the final calculation.

Amortisation: it is the total annual amortisation costs of the different parts of the vehicle (traction vehicle, body work, trailer, ancilliary systems...). In case some of these parts won't be acquired by the company (renting, etc.) the annual cost of using that particular element will be considered. The formula to calculate the amortisation costs will be the following:

$$A = \frac{C - R - N}{V}$$

where: A= annual amortisation cost of the vehicle element (euros)

C= acquisition value (VAT excluded) of the vehicle element (euros)

R= residual value (VAT excluded) of the vehicle element (euros)

N= tyres value (VAT excluded) of the vehicle element (euros)

v= useful life of the vehicle element (years)

Financing: it is the total annual financing costs of the different parts of the vehicle (traction vehicle, body work, trailer, ancilliary systems...). The formula to calculate the financing costs will be the following (assuming annual instalments):

$$F = \frac{\left(n \cdot \frac{P \cdot i \cdot j}{j - 1} \right) - P}{v}$$

where: F= annual financing cost of the vehicle element (euros)

P= loan required to buy the vehicle element (euros)

i= interest rate (percentage divided by 100)

n= financing period (years)

v= useful life of the vehicle element (years)

j= $(1+i)^n$

Drivers costs: it is the total annual cost of the driving personnel of the vehicles (subsistence allowance not included here).

Vehicle insurance: it is the total annual cost of the vehicles insurance.

Tax costs: it is the total annual fiscal cost of the vehicles.

Fuel: it is the total annual cost of the fuel used by the traction vehicle and all the equipment. The formula to calculate the annual fuel costs will be the following:

$$C = c_v + c_e$$

$$c_v = \frac{pv \cdot cv \cdot k}{100}$$

$$c_e = pe \cdot ce \cdot h$$

where:

- C= annual total fuel cost (euros)
- C_v= annual fuel cost of the traction vehicle (euros)
- C_e= annual fuel cost of the equipment (euros)
- pv= fuel purchase price (VAT excluded) of the traction vehicle (euros / litre)
- cv= average fuel consumption of the traction vehicle (litres / 100 kilometres)
- k= kilometres travelled annually by the traction system (kilometres)
- pe= fuel purchase price (VAT excluded) of the equipment (euros / litre)
- ce= average fuel consumption of the equipment (litres / hour)
- h= annual operating hours of the equipment (hours)

Urea solution: it is the total annual cost (VAT excluded) of the urea solution consumed by the vehicle.

Tyres: it is the total annual cost of the different types of tyres. The formula to calculate the tyres costs will be the following:

$$N = \frac{p \cdot n \cdot k}{D}$$

where: N= annual cost of a specific type of tyre (euros)
p= purchase price (VAT excluded) of replacing that particular type of tire (euros)
n= number of tyres of that particular type
k= kilometres travelled annually by the vehicle (kilometres)
d= average life of that tire type (kilometres)

Maintenance: it is the total annual maintenance costs of the vehicle and the equipment. The formula to calculate the annual maintenance costs will be the following:

$$M = m \cdot k$$

where: M= annual maintenance cost (euros)
m= maintenance cost per km (VAT excluded) of the vehicle and equipment (euros / kilometre)
k= kilometres travelled annually by the vehicle (kilometres)

Repairs: it is the total annual repairing costs of the vehicle and the equipment. The formula to calculate the annual repairing costs will be the following:

$$R = r \cdot k$$

where: R= annual repairing cost (euros)
r= repairing cost per km (VAT excluded) of the vehicle and equipment (euros / kilometre)
k= kilometres travelled annually by the vehicle (kilometres)

Subsistence allowance: it is the total annual costs of the driving personnel subsistence allowances.

Tolls: it is the total annual cost of the tolls required to be paid by the vehicle.

Indirect costs: it is the total annual cost of the indirect costs associated to that vehicle.

Based on this methodology the following costs per km have been obtained for the different type of vehicles and will be used to estimate the transportation costs in the reverse logistics chain:

	Cost per km (empty)	Cost per km (loaded)
Van	0,9770 €/km	1,3026 €/km
Articulated Lorry (general load)	1,0683 €/km	1,2568 €/km
2-Axle Rigid Lorry (general load)	0,9285 €/km	1,1606 €/km
Vehicle carrier truck	1,2294 €/km	1,5368 €/km
Industrial vehicle carrier truck	1,3142 €/km	1,4602 €/km
Articulated dump truck for bulk	1,0503 €/km	1,3128 €/km
Container truck	1,1193 €/km	1,3169 €/km

Table 11 – Transportation costs per km (empty and loaded)

7.2 Logistics platform

This subsection details all the fields (or tables) in the database, indicating their type and a brief description to indicate what they are used for. These tables are formed by attributes that admit a value of a certain type, such as numeric (integer or double) or text (string). The fields that are shared by all the tables ("createdAt" and "updatedAt") indicate the date and time in which a specific entry is created or updated respectively in that table of the DB.

7.2.1 User table

This table manages the data of the registered users who will have access to the application, as well as the encrypted attributes for their access.

Variable	Type	Description
id	Integer	User identifier
username	String	Name of the user in the system
password	String	Encrypted password for user access
email	String	Email of the user in the system

Table 12 – User table logistics DB

7.2.2 Locations table

This table manages the data related to the locations available in the project. Coordinates, addresses and company type.

Variable	Tipo	Description
id	Integer	Location identifier
user_id	Integer	Foreign key to join with the user's table
lat	Long	Coordinate of latitude
lng	Long	Coordinate of longitude
company	String	Name of the company
address	String	Address name
company_type	String	Role of the company in the value chain

Table 13 – Locations table logistics DB

7.2.3 Transport table

This table manages the data related to the transport information from an origin location to a destination, with the available information of the transport carried out on the way.

Variable	Tipo	Description
id	Integer	Transport identifier
origin	Integer	Foreign key to join with the locations table
destination	Long	Foreign key to relate with the product identifier
transport	json	Transport details in json format

Table 14 – Transport table logistics DB

7.2.4 Costs table

This table manages the data used to make the reverse logistics transport calculations.

Variable	Tipo	Description
id	Integer	Transport identifier
Vehicle_type	Enum	Type of vehicle used
Cost_empty	double	Cost per km of an empty vehicle of the assigned type
Cost_loaded	double	Cost per km of a loaded vehicle of the assigned type

Table 15 – Costs table logistics DB

7.3 Integration into the ECOBULK environment

The Logistics Platform must be able to communicate with the others softwares in the ECOBULK environment. For this purpose, an Application Program Interface (API) has been developed. In order to maintain this service secure, an authorization protocol based on tokens has been implemented.

An API acts as an interface between two different applications so that they can communicate with each other. Typically an API is web based, "HTTP" is the most commonly used protocol for communication. An API generally involves calling functions from within a software program and consists of a complete set of rules and specifications for a software program to follow in order to facilitate interaction.

Typical operations related to HTTP protocol are:

- **GET:** Read operation, returns the selected information without modifying it.
- **POST:** Creation operation, creates a new entry with the information passed in the body of the message.
- **PUT:** Update operation, modifies all or part of an existing information entry.
- **DELETE:** Deleting operation, deletes the selected information.

The following are the access links used in our API. In the links, the initial part of the URL is omitted for better compression. The elements of the link that contain a (<>) are the arguments or variables and

will take a specific value according to the type of variable they represent, for example, (<location_id>) will take the value of an integer that represents a specific location.

7.3.1 User API calls

POST	/api/users	Create a user
Header		
Content-Type	application/json	
Body		
<pre>{ "email": "<>", "password": "<>", "name": "<>" }</pre>		
Responses		
200	User created successfully	

POST	/api/users/login	Login as user
Header		
Content-Type	application/json	
Body		
<pre>{ "email": "<>", "password": "<>" }</pre>		
Responses		
200	Gives back a token to make calls authorized calls to the API	
400	Invalid credentials	

GET	/api/users/me	Check user information
Header		
Content-Type	application/json	
api-token	<token>	
Body		
N/A		
Responses		
204	User credentials	

PUT	/api/users/me	Edit user information
-----	---------------	-----------------------

Header	
Content-Type	application/json
api-token	<token >
Body	
<pre>{ "email": "<>", "password": "<>", "name": "<>" }</pre>	
Responses	
200	Updated user information
400	Format error

DELETE	/api/users/me	Delete user
Header		
Content-Type	application/json	
api-token	<token>	
Body		
N/A		
Responses		
204	User deleted successfully	

7.3.2 Location API calls

POST	/api/location	Create a new location
Header		
Content-Type	application/json	
api-token	<token>	
Body		
<pre>{ "name": "<>", "company": "<>", "latitude": "<>", "longitude": "<>" }</pre>		
Responses		
200	Location created successfully	
400	Invalid credentials	

GET	/api/location/<location_id>	Check location info
Header		
Content-Type	application/json	
api-token	<token>	
Body		
N/A		

Responses	
200	Location information

PUT	/api/location/<location_id>	Update location info
Header		
Content-Type	application/json	
api-token	<token >	
Body		
<pre>{ "name": "<>", "company": "<>", "latitude": "<>", "longititude": "<>" }</pre>		
Responses		
200	Updated location information	
400	Format error	

DELETE	/api/location/<location_id>	Delete location
Header		
Content-Type	application/json	
api-token	<token>	
Body		
N/A		
Responses		
204	Location deleted successfully	

7.3.3 Transport API calls

POST	/api/path/<product_id>	Add a product change of location
Header		
Content-Type	application/json	
api-token	<token>	
Body		
<pre>{ "product_id": "<product_id>", "origin": "<location_id>", "destination": "<location_id>", "transport": <json> }</pre>		
Responses		
200	Path added successfully	
400	Invalid credentials	

GET	/api/path/<product_id>	Get the path of a given product
Header		
Content-Type		application/json
api-token		<token>
Body		
N/A		
Responses		
200		Location information
400		Invalid product_id

7.3.4 Reverse logistics API calls

GET	/api/reverse/logistics/<product_id>	Reverse logistics cost
Header		
Content-Type		application/json
api-token		<token>
Body		
<pre>{ "destination": "<location_id or all>", "vehicle_type": "<>" }</pre>		
Responses		
200		Reverse logistics information
400		Invalid product_id

8 Conclusions and next steps

This deliverable has covered, first, the definition of the SCOR model for the reverse logistics of the three sectors and then later, an analysis SWOT on the circular models have been developed.

Furthermore, the labelling and tracking system description and choice, together with a methodology to study the environmental impact and the transportation costs of every possible path in a reverse logistics context.

The logistics platform developed in this deliverable will be capable of giving the DSS the costs of every possible path to include this information in AI algorithm to decide the best final option to circular action.

The next steps will be to incorporate a proper communication of this logistics platform with the rest of the ECOBULK environment and prove its validity in the pilots that will be conducted on WP4 of ECOBULK project.

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